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Review Article

**REVIEW OF THE EFFECTS OF CHILDHOOD ABUSE ON
MEDICAL OUTCOMES**

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Abstract:

This review article provides a critical review of studies assessing the effects of the health of infants, children abused. During the last decades, a large amount of studies and literature reviews on the consequences of child sexual abuse has been appeared. Child abuse and neglect, is the extent to which society is not well known, most of the times that are hidden, many more victims does not mention in a public health problem. World Health Organization, children's health, adversely affects the physical or psychosocial development, an adult, knowingly or unknowingly, in the community or by the government accepts all the same behavior as child abuse. Abused and neglected child reaches very few therapeutic institutions. Generally, the cases remain hidden in the family. If the situation was brought in the emergency department is often heavy, life-threatening complications.

Key Words: Sexual abuse, child abuse, prevention, depression, sexualized behavior.

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INTRODUCTION:

Childhood sexual abuse is a complex life experience, not a diagnosis or a disorder. An array of sexual activities is covered by the term child sexual abuse (CSA) [1]. These include intercourse, attempted intercourse, oral-genital contact, fondling of genitals directly or through clothing, exhibitionism or exposing children to adult sexual activity or pornography, and the use of the child for prostitution or pornography. This diversity alone ensures that there will be a range of outcomes. In addition, the age and gender of the child, the age and gender of the perpetrator, the nature of the relationship between the child and perpetrator, and the number, frequency, and duration of the abuse experiences all appear to influence some outcomes [2]. Thus sexually abused children constitute a very heterogeneous group with many degrees of abuse about whom few simple generalizations hold. The outcomes summarized in this review are based on studies in which the majority of subjects experienced more severe forms of sexual abuse, generally including some form of child or adult genital contact. In the following decades, the incidence based on official statistics increased dramatically. Although much of this apparent increase probably reflected a growing awareness among the public and professionals, some studies suggest that the overall incidence of child abuse and neglect increased. Using as official observers a variety of professionals who routinely came in contact with children, counting both reported and non reported cases, the series of National Incidence Studies found a 67% increase in all forms of child abuse from 1986 to 1993[3]. Officially reported cases of CSA, however, declined during this same period. There is little agreement on reasons for this decline or whether it represents a decline in actual cases. In 2000 (most recent data available) CSA constituted approximately 10% of all officially reported child abuse cases and numbered approximately 88,000 substantiated or indicated cases, a 41% decrease from the peak estimate of 149,800 cases in 1992. Statistics on the prevalence of CSA are derived primarily from retrospective accounts by adults and can be roughly divided into studies using clinical versus nonclinical samples. It is not surprising that prevalence figures vary widely as a function of the selection and response rate, the definition used, and the method (e.g., self-report versus structured interview) by which an abuse history is obtained. Community samples typically range from 12% to 35% of women and 4% to 9% of men reporting an unwanted sexual experience prior to age 18 years. Adjusting for sample-related variation, response rates, and differences in definitions across 16 cross-sectional community sample surveys, Gorey and Leslie (1997)

calculated the prevalence of CSA as 16.8% for women and 7.9% for men. Large community survey studies of the incidence and prevalence of CSA in children and adolescents are rare. The most comprehensive study to date is a telephone survey of 2000 children aged 10 to 16 years conducted [4]. For the year preceding the interview, they found an incidence rate of 3.2% for girls and 0.6% for boys for contact CSA, defined as "...a perpetrator touching the sexual parts of a child under or over the clothing, penetrating the child, or engaging in any oral-genital contact with the child". The lifetime prevalence rate for a combination of the attempted and completed CSA categories was 10.5% for the overall sample. When they are available, rates of CSA in other countries are reasonably comparable with those found in the United States. A review of large sample population based studies in 19 countries found a range of prevalence rates of 7% to 36% for females and 3% to 29% for males. Female-to-male ratios were typically between 1.5:1 and 3:1. Across all the studies, only about half of victims had disclosed to anyone [5].

Girls are at about 2.5 to 3 times higher risk than boys, although approximately 22% to 29% of all CSA victims are male. Boys are underrepresented in psychiatric samples, especially older boys who may be reluctant to disclose or who may be shunted into the criminal justice or substance abuse treatment systems. Research indicates that mental health professionals rarely ask adult males about childhood sexual abuse [6]. Age Risk for CSA rises with age. Data from 1996 indicate that approximately 10% of victims are between ages 0 and 3 years. Between ages 4 and 7 years, the percentage almost triples (28.4%). Ages 8 to 11 years account for a quarter (25.5%) of cases, with children 12 years and older accounting for the remaining third (35.9%) of cases. Some authorities believe that, as a risk factor, age operates differentially for girls and boys, with high risk starting earlier and lasting longer for girls. Disabilities Physical disabilities, especially those that impair a child's perceived credibility such as blindness, deafness, and mental retardation, are associated with increased risk. Three factors seem to contribute to this increased vulnerability: dependency, institutional care, and communication difficulties [7]. There appears to be a gender effect such that boys are overrepresented among sexually abused children with disabilities compared with their respective proportion of sexually abused children without disabilities. Family Constellation Family constellation, particularly the absence of one or both parents, is a significant risk factor. The presence of a

stepfather in the home doubles the risk for girls, not only for being abused by the stepfather but also for being abused by other men prior to the arrival of the stepfather in the home (Mullen et al., 1993). Parental impairments, particularly maternal illness, maternal alcoholism, extended maternal absences, serious marital conflicts, parental substance abuse, social isolation, and punitive parenting, have all been associated with increased risk in some studies. Clinically, the presence of abused siblings is thought to increase the child's risk, although this has not been empirically established [8].

More recent studies with randomized assignment to different treatment conditions indicate that session-limited cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) is effective for some symptoms in sexually abused children. Many studies compared 100 sexually abused children randomized to four treatment conditions: a 12-week abuse-focused CBT model for the child only, CBT for the parent only, CBT for both parent and child, and standardized community care. All groups improved, but CBT provided directly to the child resulted in the most benefit. Two studies by Cohen and Mannarino (1996, 1998) included a non-offending parent in both the CBT and non-directive supportive therapy components. In the first study (N=67) of 3- to 7-year-olds, children receiving CBT showed significant improvement in PTSD symptoms and internalizing, externalizing, and sexually inappropriate behaviors that were sustained over 1 year. A second study of 49 older children showed significant improvement for depression and social competence in those receiving abuse-focused CBT versus non-directive supportive therapy [10]. Celano et al. (1996) also found that abuse-focused CBT was superior to nonspecific treatment for sexually abused girls and their parents. A 12-week follow-up of CBT-treated sexually abused children (n= 18) compared with waiting list controls (n= 10) also found significant reductions in PTSD symptoms. Thus abuse-focused CBT models provided to the child—often together with similar treatment to a non-offending parent—are currently the best-documented, effective treatments for CSA. A number of symptoms, especially aggression and sexualized behavior, remain largely resistant to these approaches, however [11].

Although several theoretical explanations of how child sexual abuse affects children's development have been proposed, in the absence of consistent empirical evidence, theories accounting for the impact of child abuse on human development lack support. Much of the controversy in the literature may be a reflection of the differences between studies

as well as of the methodological limitations of the literature. Many studies are characterized by serious design and measurement problems, including poor sampling methods, absence of matched comparison groups, and inadequate control for effect modifiers and confounders [12]. Moreover, many literature reviews are characterized by imprecision and subjectivity. For example, some reviewers have specified neither the data sources that were searched nor the criteria used for including studies, paying more attention to study findings indicating harmful effects. A more objective process has been provided by some meta-analytic reviews, which have attempted to infer whether child sexual abuse is significantly associated with specific outcomes and to estimate the strength of this association [13]. Based on the transformation of the results of all the relevant studies to a common statistical metric, which are then combined into one overall statistic, these reviews have used a more rigorous and transparent approach to reduce the potential for bias, avoiding imprecision and subjectivity [14].

DISCUSSION:

Child abuse or child maltreatment is physical, sexual, or psychological maltreatment or neglect of a child or children, especially by a parent or other caregiver. Child abuse may include any act or failure to act by a parent or other caregiver that results in actual or potential harm to a child, and can occur in a child's home, or in the organizations, schools or communities the child interacts with.

The terms child abuse and child maltreatment are often used interchangeably, although some researchers make a distinction between them, treating child maltreatment as an umbrella term to cover neglect, exploitation, and trafficking [1-7].

Different jurisdictions have developed their own definitions of what constitutes child abuse for the purposes of removing children from their families or prosecuting a criminal charge. Child sexual abuse (CSA) is a form of child abuse in which an adult or older adolescent abuses a child for sexual stimulation. Sexual abuse refers to the participation of a child in a sexual act aimed toward the physical gratification or the financial profit of the person committing the act. Forms of CSA include asking or pressuring a child to engage in sexual activities (regardless of the outcome), indecent exposure of the genitals to a child, displaying pornography to a child, actual sexual contact with a child, physical contact with the child's genitals, viewing of the child's genitalia without physical contact, or using a child to produce child pornography. Selling the sexual

services of children may be viewed and treated as child abuse rather than simple incarceration [15-18].

Effects of child sexual abuse on the victim(s) include guilt and self-blame, flashbacks, nightmares, insomnia, fear of things associated with the abuse (including objects, smells, places, doctor's visits, etc.), self-esteem difficulties, sexual dysfunction, chronic pain, addiction, self-injury, suicidal ideation, somatic complaints, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, other mental illnesses including borderline personality disorder and dissociative identity disorder, propensity to re-victimization in adulthood, bulimia nervosa, and physical injury to the child, among other problems. Children who are the victims are also at an increased risk of sexually transmitted infections due to their immature immune systems and a high potential for mucosal tears during forced sexual contact. Sexual victimization at a young age has been correlated with several risk factors for contracting HIV including decreased knowledge of sexual topics, increased prevalence of HIV, engagement in risky sexual practices, condom avoidance, lower knowledge of safe sex practices, frequent changing of sexual partners, and more years of sexual activity [19-22].

In the United States, approximately 15% to 25% of women and 5% to 15% of men were sexually abused when they were children. Most sexual abuse offenders are acquainted with their victims; approximately 30% are relatives of the child, most often brothers, sisters, fathers, mothers, uncles or cousins; around 60% are other acquaintances such as friends of the family, babysitters, or neighbours; strangers are the offenders in approximately 10% of child sexual abuse cases. In over one-third of cases, the perpetrator is also a minor.

In 1999 the BBC reported on the RAHI Foundation's survey of sexual abuse in India, in which 76% of respondents said they had been abused as children, 40% of those stating the perpetrator was a family member.

31 empirical studies reviewed above provide overwhelming evidence that children who live in maritally violent homes are at risk for being physically abused. Using a variety of samples and approaches, the studies have provided data strongly in agreement that there is considerable co-occurrence of domestic violence and physical child abuse. Sixteen of the twenty studies (80%) using samples of either battered women or abused children found co-occurrence rates

of 40% or more. However, it should be kept in mind that those rates vastly overestimate the extent of co-occurrence that occurs in the community. On the basis of the two relatively large-scale representative samples that used a liberal definition of physical child abuse, we conclude that about 6% of children in the United States are likely to be physically maltreated in any given year in families in which there is marital violence. Despite the predominance of evidence that the rate of co-occurrence is a high one, the widely fluctuating rates of co-occurrence across studies is disturbing. Some studies have indicated that virtually all of the children in maritally violent homes are physically abused, in contrast to other studies that have found that the rate may be under 30%. To some extent, those extreme differences, as well as many of the apparent fluctuations, can be accounted for by methodological reasons. Indeed, methodological inconsistencies across studies represented the largest impediment to arriving at an accurate [23-27].

The Adverse Childhood Experiences Study is a long-running investigation into the relationship between childhood adversity, including various forms of abuse and neglect, and health problems in later life. The initial phase of the study was conducted in San Diego, California from 1995 to 1997.[81] The World Health Organization summarizes the study's findings as follows: The Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) study, in which some 17,300 middle-aged, middle-class and mostly employed residents of the state of California participated, suggests that childhood maltreatment and household dysfunction contribute to the development – decades later – of the chronic diseases that are the most common causes of death and disability in the United States. The study examined the long-term effects of maltreatment and household dysfunction during childhood, including: psychological, physical and sexual abuse; violence against the mother; and living with household members who were either substance abusers, mentally ill or suicidal, or else had been in prison [28-32]. A strong relationship was seen between the number of adverse experiences (including physical and sexual abuse in childhood) and self-reports of cigarette smoking, obesity, physical inactivity, alcoholism, drug abuse, depression, attempted suicide, sexual promiscuity and sexually transmitted diseases in later life. Furthermore, people who reported higher numbers of negative experiences in childhood were much more likely to exhibit multiple health-risk behaviours, which the study suggested were adopted as coping devices. Similarly, the more

adverse childhood experiences reported, the more likely the person was to have heart disease, cancer, stroke, diabetes, skeletal fractures, liver disease and poor health as an adult. Maltreatment and other adverse childhood experiences may thus be among the basic factors that underlie health risks, illness and death, and could be identified by routine screening of all patients. Although the ACE study and its findings relate to a specific population within the United States, it is reasonable to assume that similar trends might be found in countries with different levels of economic and social development [33-36].

CONCLUSIONS:

The findings suggest that preventing child abuse is not simply a matter of parents doing a better job, but rather it is about creating a context in which “doing better” is easier. Enlightened public policy and the replication of high-quality publicly supported interventions are only part of what is needed to successfully combat child abuse. It remains important to remind the public that child abuse and neglect are serious threats to a child’s healthy development and that overt violence toward children and a persistent lack of attention to their care and supervision are unacceptable. Individuals have the ability to accept personal responsibility for reducing acts of child abuse and neglect by providing support to each other and offering protection to all children within their family and their community.

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